

ELIXIR Commissioned Service: Training Platform 2024-2026 Work Plan

D4.4- The TtT webpages/portal in the Training SPLASH

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the technical development and structural redesign of the ELIXIR-GOBLET [Train-the-Trainer \(TtT\) webpages within the ELIXIR Training SPLASH platform](#). The work builds upon [D4.3](#) and consolidates the technical framework for representing TtT programme, the TtT trainers and community, the TtT lessons, by implementing metadata-driven structures, dedicated layouts for rendering trainer and module pages, and integration of dynamically updated TtT events through the ELIXIR TeSS widget. These components establish a coherent and extensible technical basis for the TtT portal within training SPLASH. All changes were reviewed within the ELIXIR Training Platform and ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer community and approved through the training SPLASH editorial workflow.

Document info

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TtT	ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer
SPLASH	Skills, Professional development, Learning Assessment, Support and Help for impactful training
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
PID	Persistent Identifier

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Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable was to provide a coherent and maintainable technical foundation for presenting TtT content within training SPLASH by implementing a complete structural framework for trainer profiles, module pages, navigational components, and dynamic event retrieval.

Description of Work

Objectives

- To extend the work of [D4.3](#) by defining unified metadata structures for TtT trainers and modules, enabling consistent parsing and rendering across training SPLASH.
- To implement dedicated layout templates and component-based rendering (trainer profiles, module pages, and card-based listings) to standardise presentation and navigation.
- To establish a coherent information architecture through collection-based organisation, permalink rules, and layout scoping, ensuring maintainability and alignment with training SPLASH technical standards.

Implementation

The implementation of the TtT portal is based primarily on pull request (PR) [#243](#), which provides the redesigned structure, layouts, metadata schema, and rendering components, and PR [#145](#), which integrates dynamic event retrieval.

1. Structural consolidation and layout redesign (PR [#243](#))

Key elements include:

- creation of the `ttt_community` collection for structured trainer metadata;
- introduction of dedicated layouts (`profile.html` and `module.html`) for rendering trainer and module pages;
- implementation of component-based index views (`ttt-community-cards.html` and `ttt-modules-cards.html`);
- updates to `_config.yml` defining collection scopes, layout assignment, and permalink rules.

These changes consolidate the technical foundations required for representing TtT resources consistently across training SPLASH.

2. Trainer profiles (PR [#243](#))

[Trainer profiles](#) are defined as individual markdown files containing structured front-matter fields, including:

- name, organisation, location,
- optional image, ORCID, GitHub, email,
- session identifiers.

The profile.html layout renders these fields into a standardised profile view, including:

- header block with trainer metadata,
- external identifiers (GitHub/ORCID/email),
- session badges,
- biography content.

All trainer profiles are displayed on the TtT landing page through the card-based ttt-community-cards component, providing a navigable index.

3. Module profiles (PR [#243](#))

[Module cards](#) were created and they are linked to the respective lessons in the [ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer GitHub](#) (PR [#296](#)), which was created using the ELIXIR Lesson template from the Training Platform. The content of the modules is updated through D4.2

4. TeSS events integration (PR [#145](#))

The [ELIXIR TeSS widget](#) is integrated into the TtT portal as documented in PR [#145](#). This component:

- retrieves TtT-related events from TeSS,
- displays a dynamic list of upcoming courses within the TtT page,
- provides direct links to full TeSS records.

Results

The updated [ELIXIR-GOBLET-TtT subpage](#) includes:

- consolidated technical structures for trainer and module pages;
- metadata-driven rendering of profiles and modules, component-based navigation between TtT resources;
- integration of dynamically updated TtT events;
- an extendable foundation for future programme content and additional modules.

Dissemination Plans

The [ELIXIR-GOBLET-TtT](#) is available as the [ELIXIR Training SPLASH](#) resource.